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**Eye movement modelling and the development of competencies for digital reading:
does the effect hold among Brazilian students?**

Juliana do Amaral

Department of Vernacular Languages and Literature – DLLV

Center of Communication and Expression – CCE

Federal University of Santa Catarina – UFSC

Florianópolis, Santa Catarina

email: juliana.amaral@ufsc.br

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1024-6066>

Mailce Borges Mota

Department of Foreign Languages and Literature – DLLE

Center of Communication and Expression – CCE

Federal University of Santa Catarina – UFSC

Florianópolis, Santa Catarina

email: mailce.mota@ufsc.br

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8674-2480>

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Abstract

The use of search engine tools for learning and exploratory tasks requires the development of digital competencies such as navigation across results and webpages, evaluation of content reliability and source credibility, and integration among multiple texts, which might convey opposing perspectives on the same issue. Digital competencies can be developed through video-based instruction with eye-movement modelling examples (EMMEs), with tried-and-tested positive effects in L1 (Salmerón et al. 2020) and L2 contexts (Do Amaral et al., 2025). The premise is that watching EMMEs increases navigation and evaluation performance in future tasks, with extended effects on prior belief update. However, research on digital reading competencies is mostly situated in north American and European countries. This study aims to test whether the effectiveness of instruction with EMMEs is replicable in Brazil among a similar sample profile (undergraduates). To this aim, a version of the EMMEs material was developed with websites and instructions in Portuguese. Using eye-tracking and pre-post design with experimental and control groups (Salmerón et al., 2020), we investigate whether watching EMMEs increases performance on a subsequent navigation task. This task simulated search results comprising four webpages about learning styles (t1) and sports supplementation (t2). Webpages presented either favorable or contrary views on each topic, interspersed. Performance will be measured in terms of a) fixations on search engine results; b) fixation on source information and reliable pages; c) integrated understanding (to be checked in a writing task), and d) prior belief update (pre/posttest). The control group will watch a video about digital competencies of similar duration. Linear regression models will be used for data analysis with group as predictor and fixation on a) search results page, b) website banner and author information, c) reliable pages, and d) position and citations in the writing task as response variables.

Keywords: EMMEs, eye movement modelling, digital reading competencies, replication

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1 INTRODUCTION

The popularisation of search engines like Google was a watershed in the use of the internet to explore textual sources of knowledge. However, reading in the age of misinformation has become more than a comprehension task. Search engine results are not ranked by content relevance, but rather by paid advertisements and popular pages i.e., those with high access (Machado et al, 2020). In addition, the webpages linked in the search might either corroborate or oppose each other, or simply provide misinformation (Marten et al., 2025). Therefore, it is left to the reader the job of identifying what is true and whom to believe (Braasch et al., 2014).

The readers' standards for coherence and evaluation vary according to the goals set and the type of task (Rouet et al., 2017). Exploratory tasks in which the reader has little prior knowledge and reads to learn recruit deeper processing compared to more simple lookup tasks involving facts and known items (Dosso et al., 2024). Exploratory tasks also involve self-regulation processes that coordinate the competencies needed to successfully navigate online.

The framework developed by Salmerón et al. (2018) proposes three competencies for digital reading: navigation, evaluation and integration. Navigation refers to inspection of the search engine results by attending to features such as the presence of paid advertisements, AI overview, and the URL (.org, .com), snippet and date within each result. Evaluation comprises both assessing content reliability through sourcing parameters such as type of webpage (blog, commercial website), institution and/or author expertise and position. Integration is the process of constructing an integrated mental representation of these pieces of information, being usually measured in writing tasks such as essays and answers to open-ended questions.

The eye tracking technology can be used not only to investigate reader's online processing of webpages but also to teach digital reading competencies through eye-movement modelling examples – EMMEs. This format of instruction uses eye movement recording to model the behaviour of an expert as they perform the task onscreen. The assumption is that watching the model's gaze might trigger the student's metacognitive awareness and positively affect behaviour in future reading tasks (Scheiter et al., 2018). Previous research found positive effects of EMMEs in the development of navigation, evaluation of content reliability and source trustworthiness in L1 (Salmerón; Llorens, 2019; Salmerón et al., 2020) and L2 (Do Amaral et al., 2025). However, there is little to no evidence of the effectiveness of this instructional approach in the Latin American context. To our knowledge, this is the first study to test the validity of EMMEs in the development of digital reading competencies among Brazilian students.

1.1 Connectivity and digital reading: the Brazilian context

It is a challenge to investigate digital reading in a country where the mean reading proficiency score in Pisa 2018 was 413 points, situating Brazil in 55th among the 79 countries assessed (Brasil, 2020). The performance of young Brazilians is below the average of OECD countries and partners in all cognitive processes assessed (locating, understanding and evaluating information, and understanding multiple sources) – which take into account changes in reading literacy in the face of emerging technologies.

Internet use is widespread and frequent in Brazil. In 2024, 93.6% of homes had internet access. Purpose ranges from communication (calls/messaging apps) to entertainment purposes such as watching series and movies, using social media, listening to music and podcasts, and reading (IBGE, 2025). Although increased connectivity is a positive result of public policies for digital inclusion, the ubiquity of digital devices has negative effects on learning. In the US, analysis of data from 149.400 4th grade students and 144.900 8th grade students who took the National Assessment of Educational progress contrasted reported frequency of portable devices in the Language & Arts class with reading comprehension tests. The results indicated a

correlation between high frequency of use and low reading comprehension scores (Salmerón et al., 2023). Concern with the effects of smartphones on students' mental health and academic achievement led to the prohibition of the device for personal use in Brazilian schools by law 15100/2025. The message is clear: not only is it necessary to democratise internet access but also to foster its conscious use.

This context highlights the importance of public policies that promote the development of reading skills considering their processes of digitisation. The Brazilian National Common Core Curriculum (BNCC, 2018, p.61) emphasises the role of schools in developing a critical stance towards the proliferation of new media, as well as its conscious use in the classroom with a view to educating for “more democratic uses of technologies and more conscious participation in the digital culture” (BNCC, 2018, p.61, my translation). The document also mentions the development of evaluation skills among students, arguing that the massive use of the internet does not imply “taking into account the ethical, aesthetic and political dimensions of this use, nor dealing critically with the content that circulates on the Web” (p.68, my translation).

In Brazil, research in digital reading has been mostly situated within the realm of discourse and literacy studies. Digital literacies are described as a set of socially situated practices needed to navigate online environments. These practices comprise basic computer skills, knowledge of how information is organized online, reading and navigation strategies (Buzato, 2009; Ribeiro, 2009). Coscarelli (2017) conceptualizes multiple document reading in digital environments as a process of investigation that involves the formulation of research questions. She proposes three categories of strategies for multiple source reading: locating and evaluating, synthesizing and integrating, and reflecting. These authors contributed to construct an understanding of digital reading and its unique features in the Brazilian context.

Experimental studies in Brazil sought to trace students' profile in online environments. Correia Almeida (2020) investigated digital literacy experiences of 10 undergraduate students

in a distance education course. The instruments were an online questionnaire and a simulated navigation task. Results indicated that students understand the organization of the learning environment, the tools available, and successfully employed strategies for navigation and reading. However, they display poor navigation and evaluation competence when using a search engine.

Almeida and colleagues (2022) investigated the strategies used by Brazilian adolescents (n=61) to evaluate the credibility of information sources through focus groups, guided internet search and interviews. Expertise and reputation were the most cited criteria for source credibility. The authors propose a framework to analyse adolescents' information evaluation comprising three navigation regimes: dilettante (in which navigation is driven by personal interest, with little attention to information trustworthiness), motivated (in which navigation is topic-driven and evaluation is affected by source reputation), and constrained (in which navigation is driven by an extrinsic learning goal and the sources selected are either known or reputable).

The scarcity of experimental research in digital reading in Brazil is alarming. In addition, no study in this context explored eye movement modelling examples (EMMEs) as a means of instruction. Because research in this field has been concentrated in European and North American countries, it remains to be confirmed whether the results from these studies confirm in the global south. Replication studies are a necessary procedure to safely affirm that the research results are reliable and can be generalized (Munafò et al., 2017).

Therefore, our study aims to test the replicability of the findings of previous studies carried out in the Spanish context (Salmeron et al. 2020; Do Amaral et al., 2025) by investigating whether the known effects of EMMEs on navigation and evaluation extend to a Brazilian population of university students. Because we aim to reach the same conclusions as Salmerón and colleagues (2020) with data from a new population at a different laboratory but same experimental design (pre/posttest), the study is considered a type D reproducibility

(Simkus et al., 2025). Following Do Amaral et al. (2025), we also investigate changes in prior beliefs update. A confirmation may enable us to further explore the effects of EMMEs on metacognition and learning among other populations such as high school or non-academic populations such as adults with low education levels.

1.2 The present study

The objective of this study is to test the effectiveness of EMMEs on the development of navigation, evaluation of content reliability and source quality, and multiple document integration among Brazilian undergraduate students. These competencies will be measured through performance in a navigation task at pre and posttest. Participants of both experimental and control groups will have their eye movements recorded while they read the results of a search engine to understand a controversial topic. Eye tracking will be used both as an instructional tool through eye movement modelling, and as a processing measure.

1.3 Research questions

- 1) Does instruction on digital reading competencies with EMMEs increase fixation duration on a) the search engine results page and its embedded features, b) the source features within each webpage (banner and author's photo, name, and occupation), and c) the reliable pages (as opposed to non-reliable pages)?
- 2) Is instruction with EMMEs associated with a) endorsing a scientifically valid position and b) citations to reliable sources in a subsequent writing task?
- 3) Do EMMEs affect updating of prior beliefs about sports supplementation, to be checked by differences between pre/posttest?

1.4 Hypotheses

Brazilian students, when watching video models, may demonstrate increased fixation duration on the search tool, on author information, and on reliable pages (compared to unreliable pages), as well as the construction of an evidence-based position in the response to the writing task. The hypotheses are directional: EMMEs will have a positive effect on

navigation and evaluation, which in turn increases performance in integration (measured in the writing task).

Previous research in the European context demonstrated the effectiveness of model videos in the comprehension of digital texts (Salmerón; Llorens, 2019), on increased attention to the search engine in navigation tasks in L1 (Salmerón et al., 2020) and L2 (Do Amaral et al., 2025), on decreased attention to non-reliable pages (Salmerón et al., 2020; Do Amaral et al., 2025), increased fixation on authorship, and more citations to sources at post-test (Salmerón et al., 2020).

2 METHOD

2.1 Sample characteristics

The sample of participants will be obtained from a pool of Brazilian undergraduate students enrolled either in the first or in second phase (inclusion criterion) of any university course. Students doing their second graduate course are not in the profile of potential participants (exclusion criterion). We therefore maintained the same sample characteristics as the study to be replicated (Salmerón et al., 2020), which was carried out in Spain. The aim was to test the potential generalizability of the findings to a similar population in a different country situated in the global south. The relevance of the Brazilian context is justified considering that previous EMMEs studies took place mostly in WEIRD (Western, Educated, Industrialized, Rich, Democratic) countries, which indicates the need to investigate whether the positive effects of EMMEs hold in non-WEIRD populations. Furthermore, a controlled experiment in the university laboratory will provide empirical support on the (to be confirmed) effectiveness of EMMEs among Brazilian students – which might safeguard future applications of this video modelling in other educational levels.

We performed G*power analyses with an a priori effect size set at $f = 0.40$, $\alpha = 0.05$, and $\beta = 0.20$ based on previous studies testing the effects of EMMEs on digital competencies

(Salmerón, Delgado, & Mason, 2020; Do Amaral et al., 2025). The results indicated that a total sample size of 31 participants would be needed to analyse the data using linear models and a minimum of 10 participants for repeated measures (pre/post tests). The number of participants will be increased in 10% to account for possible data loss due to technical failures or recording errors (in these cases, participant data will be excluded from the sample).

Recruitment will be done by personally inviting students during class time, via the university news portal, and social media. Participation will be voluntary. Participants will not receive any type of compensation for their participation, following the Brazilian legislation (National Council of Ethics in Research).

2.2 Instruments

2.2.1 Eye-tracking apparatus

The stimulus will consist of the research-generated webpages displayed on a 14' screen at a resolution of 1680x1050. Mangold Vision Designer was used to create the experiment. A Mangold VT3 30hz mini eye tracker connected to a desktop computer with Mangold Vision Recorder will be used to collect data. This program enables control over the experiment launch, recording and saving. Mangold Vision Analyzer is the program is used to visualize data, define AOIs and generate the output.

2.3 Materials

2.3.1 Prior beliefs questionnaire

Prior beliefs about learning styles and sports supplements (topics of the navigation tasks at t1 and t2, respectively) will be controlled both at pre and posttest, as in Do Amaral et al. (2025). The term "belief" is used in this study to refer to knowledge that is scientifically inaccurate. Prior beliefs "reflect what individuals accept as or want to be true about a particular topic" (Braasch et al. 2014, p.120). For instance, believing that cell phone radiation causes brain tumors will influence comprehension and memory for texts read in this topic – and textual sources in accordance with one's prior beliefs will be considered more reliable.

The learning styles theory is a highly pervasive misconception among undergraduate students (Menz et al., 2021; Ferrero et al., 2016). According to this theory, students learn best when materials are compatible with their predominant modality (visual, auditory, kinaesthetic, etc.). However, the theory lacks scientific validation, since preferred modality does not always result in learning gains (Kirschner, 2017). Do Amaral et al. (2025) used a section of the Misconceptions about Multimedia Learning Questionnaire (MMLQ) (Eitel et al., 2021) to measure belief in learning styles. This questionnaire investigated the presence of misconceptions about multimedia learning among a group of German teachers and undergraduate students. All statements corresponded to an inaccurate view of learning based on that theory. We used the same statements as in the original study translated to Portuguese (Table 1).

Supplements are also surrounded by misinformation and commercial interests. In particular, the use of sports supplements has been subject of controversy, even among nutritionists. While some experts recommend their use without major restrictions, others argue that only high-performance athletes should take supplements, emphasising the importance of proper nutrition and the health risks associated with unguided use. To control for prior beliefs about sports supplements, four statements were developed by the researchers representing inaccurate views about sports supplementation.

For both topics, participants had to agree/disagree with each statement and then rate the degree of certainty of their response (“Are you sure?”) on a five-point Likert scale ranging from “very sure” to “very unsure”, following the same procedure as Do Amaral et al. (2025). They were asked to answer the questionnaire quickly.

Table 1*Statements comprising the prior beliefs questionnaire*

Learning styles (Eitel et al., 2021)
LS1: Performance is decreased when visual learners study with text or when verbal learners study with animations or diagrams..
LS2: Performance is better when students work with materials that are constructed to match their learning style.
LS3: A necessary condition for good teaching is to know the students' learning style (visual, verbal, kinesiological).
LS4: Whether students learn better with visual or verbal materials depends on their learning style.
Sports supplements
SE1: The consumption of sports supplements is essential for muscle mass growth.
SE2: Healthy individuals may consume sports supplements without the supervision of a doctor or nutritionist.
SE3: The consumption of sports supplements poses no health risks.
SE4: High daily doses of sports supplements are linked to improved performance in high-intensity activities.

Source: the authors

2.3.2 Navigation task

Do Amaral et al. (2025) looked at the effects of EMMEs solely by comparing the eye movements of experimental vs. control groups in one navigation task. In the present study, we added a navigation task as baseline to enhance experimental rigour. Participants will perform two tasks: one at t1 and another at t2, after watching the EMMEs (experimental group) or another instructional video (control group). At both times, participants' eye movements will be recorded as they perform the task. Both tasks are exploratory in nature, which generally involves analysing search results in the search engine for longer and with greater focus on the documents (i.e., the content of each of the listed websites) compared to search tasks (Dosso et al., 2024).

The first navigation task (t1) consists of an adaptation and translation of the material developed by Do Amaral et al. (2025). The adaptation consisted of reducing the search results list from six to four results following the same number of webpages as the study by Salmerón, Delgado, and Mason (2020), whose design also included a baseline. The task simulates an online search in Portuguese using the search strings “learning styles”. Two pages display favourable positions and two are contrary to the misconception, arranged in an interleaved manner (table 2). The texts were translated and revised to contain one main idea each and range from 374-392 words. In their webpage format, they all contain a banner, title, name and author credentials. The texts favourable to the learning styles theory were manipulated to be perceived as unreliable sources, being presented as commercial webpages and/or by non-specialist authors; the webpages containing arguments opposing LS represent research institutions and scientific journals, and their authors were authorities in the field.

Table 2

Summary of text characteristics for t1

Título	Página web	Tipo	Posição	Autor	Extensão
Learning styles and homeschooling	https://homeschoolbrasil.com/estilos-de-aprendizagem	Commercial	Favorable	Sales manager	374 words
Learning styles – ineffective for learning and teaching	https://cienciaparaeducacao.org/estilos-de-aprendizagem	Scholar Opinion article	Contrary	Professor	385 words
How to accommodate students’ diversity	www.profacristinam.orais.blogspot.com	Blog post	Favorable	Primary school teacher	376 words
Why are Learning styles so popular?	https://www.revistas.usp.br/educacaoepequisa	Academic article	Contrary	pdD candidate	392 words

in
Education

Source: the authors

After watching the video, participants will perform a second navigation task (t2) in which they will read four webpages on the topic of dietary supplements. The LS navigation task was placed at t1 because we wanted to check whether the effects of instruction would transfer to posttest regardless of topic – which allows for a more comprehensive interpretation of the results. As in t1, a page with the list of search results and four webpages corresponding to those results were developed. The task simulates an online search using the strings “sports supplements”. Two pages describe what supplements are, demonstrating commercial interests and uncritical positions, while the other two point to risks of deliberate consumption. Uncritical and critical positions were arranged interspersed in the search results page (Table 3).

Table 3

Summary of the text characteristics for t2

Título	Página web	Tipo	Posição	Autor	Extensão
Force supplements	https://www.forcasu.com.br/elementos.com	Commercial	Favorable	Sales assistant	378 words
Supplementation or diet: which is the best way to get protein for your workout?	https://www.scielo.br/du/rbne/suplemento-s-ou-dieta	Scholar opinion article	Contrary	Doctor	358 words
Pump up your workout	https://www.anelisefonsecapersonal.blog/spot.com	Blog	Favorable	Personal trainer	359 words
Sports supplements: possible risks	https://www.anvisa.org.br/suplementos-esportivos-possiveis-riscos	National health agency	Contrary	Agency director	376 words

Source: authors

2.3.3 Writing task

Integrated comprehension will be assessed through a writing task consisting of an open-ended question. At t1, instructions are as follows: *The websites you visited present different perspectives on the topic of learning styles. Based on the knowledge you have gained from evaluating these perspectives, write an informed response to post in the WhatsApp group. You should answer the question: "Are learning styles effective for teachers and students?" (120-150 words)*. At t2, instructions are the same but the question to be answered is "Is the consumption of sports supplements recommended?" Participants have a maximum 10 minutes to answer the question.

2.3.4 Eye movement modelling examples

The eye movement modelling examples used in the current study are a revised version of the instrument developed by Do Amaral et al. (2025). One main issue with this previous stimulus was the language. The webpages in which strategies were modelled as well as the instructions were in Spanish. Therefore, a version of EMMEs for Brazilian students should consist of websites and instructions in Portuguese.

Two other adaptations were made for the Brazilian version. The first was the suppression of the strategy of *quickly abandoning topically unrelated pages* since this is no longer a pressing issue in search engines. With the evolution of algorithm accuracy, the resulting webpages tend to display mostly topic-related results. In addition, analysis of the annotations taken by students as they watched the EMMEs showed that content was a salient source feature, with access to topically unrelated pages being interpreted as poor evaluation behaviour even when readers abandon the page without reading (Do Amaral et al. in press). The second adaptation was the omission of poor models. At the time of stimulus development, there was uncertainty about whether contrasting good and poor behaviour would result in better comprehension of the competencies modelled. Video length was also considered since

experiment time increased with the addition of the baseline (t1). The skills to be focused on in this new model video are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4

Description of the strategies modelled

Estrategy modelled	Description
Inspection of sections list	Reads all the topics on the list, selects of the section relevant to the objective, and begins reading the section.
Full SERP inspection	Types keywords into the search tool and inspects the results page from top to bottom, fixating all page titles, web addresses, dates, and snippet information. Selects one relevant page at the bottom of the list.
Identification of source information	Selects a webpage and fixates the website banner, name of the institution, name, photo and credentials of the author.
Deep reading of reliable pages	Selects a webpage from the list of results, focuses on the page logo and author information, and reads the text slowly and carefully (twice).
Skimming of non-reliable pages	Selects a webpage from the list of results, focusing on the page logo and author information, leaving the page without reading the text.

Source: the authors

The strategies were recorded by the first author over the same stimuli developed for the navigation task (t1). This manipulation allows participants to first perform the navigation task and (after the writing task) watch the eye movements of a model doing the same task (experimental condition). The resulting video consisted of the models' recorded eye movements over familiar webpages in Portuguese. Familiarity would allow students to focus on the model's gaze (as they were instructed to) rather than on content. All the instructions from the original study were translated to Portuguese.

While watching the EMMEs, participants will be instructed to pause the video and take notes. The annotation sheet asks participants to provide a) a brief description of the behaviour observed and b) an assessment of the reading and analysis of the material on a Likert scale followed by lines to justify their decision.

Table 5*Study Design*

Question	Hypotheses	Sampling plan	Analysis plan	Rationale for deciding the sensitivity of the test for confirming or disconfirming the hypothesis	Interpretation given different outcomes	Theory that could be shown wrong by the outcomes
1) Does instruction on digital reading competencies with EMMEs increase fixation duration on a) the search engine page and its embedded features, b) the source features within each webpage (banner and author's photo, name, and occupation), and c) the reliable pages (as opposed to non-reliable pages)?	Participants in the experimental (EMMEs) group may demonstrate increased fixation duration on the search tool, on author information, and on reliable pages compared to controls	A priori power analysis indicated a minimum sample size of 31 participants	Linear model with Group as predictor and as response fixation duration on a) the search engine results page and its embedded features, b) the source features within each webpage (banner and author's photo, name, and occupation), and c) the reliable webpages (as opposed to non-reliable webpages).	Null hypothesis testing	Variables not accounted for; population profile	Previous research demonstrated the effectiveness of model videos on increased attention to the search engine in L1 (Salmerón et al., 2020) and L2 (Do Amaral et al., 2025), on decreased attention to non-reliable pages (Salmerón et al., 2020; Do Amaral et al., 2025), and increased fixation on authorship (Salmerón et al., 2020)
2) Is instruction with EMMEs associated with a) endorsing a scientifically valid position and b) citations	Watching EMMEs will have a positive effect on navigation and evaluation, which in turn	A priori power analysis indicated a minimum sample size of 31	Linear model with Group as predictor and as response position and	Null hypothesis testing	Variables not accounted for; population profile	Previous research observed effects of eye moment modeling on increased citations to

to reliable increases participant citations in sources at
sources in a performance s the writing post-test
subsequent in integration (measured in the writing (Salmerón et
writing task? task) al., 2020).

1) Do EMMEs affect updating of prior beliefs about sports supplementation, to be checked by differences between pre/posttest?	Watching EMMEs will have a positive effect on navigation and evaluation, which in turn fosters misconception update from pre to post test	A priori power analysis indicated a minimum sample size of 10 participant s	Linear model with Group as predictor and pre/post test as response	Null hypothesis testing	Variables not accounted for; population profile	Prior belief update was observed in a previous study in L2 reading (Do Amaral et al., 2025)
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Source: the authors.

2.4 Procedures

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the Federal University of Santa Catarina – CEP/UFSC (protocol number 7.469.720), and the research questions and hypotheses were preregistered at the Open Science Framework platform (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TYCXK>). A pilot study was carried out with 6 participants to test the instruments, the clarity of the instructions, and the time needed to perform each of the tasks. Because sample size was small, these data did not undergo analysis. However, it available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20215751> .

Prior to participation, students will be duly informed about the experiment and the possible risks and benefits the study involves. After being informed, they will be asked to read and sign the Free Informed Consent Form. First, all participants will answer demographic questions and will have their prior beliefs in learning styles and sports supplementation measured in a questionnaire. At the navigation task at t1, they will read the results of an online search about learning styles and the four webpages that comprise the results while their eye movements are being recorded. Maximum time for task completion was set to 20’ based on mean time in the pilot study. Task instructions are as follows:

Now you will read websites while we record your eye movements about learning styles. This is a very controversial theory. While some believe that each student has a

way of learning, others argue that this is a myth. Someone posted a video about this theory in the family group and your cousin said it was false. To learn more, you will read the results of a Google search on this topic. You don't have to read everything, but you must access the four pages to evaluate the sources and content and then answer the question. You can use the scroll button to move up and down the pages and also the mouse to click on the links. You can also go back to a page if you want, within the established time (10 minutes). I'll let you know when there are two minutes left. First, we will do the calibration. After that, you cannot move much.

Next, participants will answer an open-ended question on the topic. Time for writing was set to maximum 10' following mean task completion time in the pilot study. Afterwards, they will be randomly assigned to either the experimental or control conditions. The experimental group will watch the video of eye-movement modelling examples (EMMEs) and take notes. The control group will watch another video about digital competencies and also take notes. At t2, all participants will read another page of search results, this time about sports supplementation. Instructions are similar to t1. Last, they will answer the open-ended question about the topic and the posttest (a repeated measure consisting of same questions on prior beliefs answered at pre-test).

Figure 2 – diagram of the procedures

ALT: The diagram describes the procedures involved in data collection: demographics, prior beliefs pretest, navigation task (t1), writing task (t1), watching the EMMEs or a control video, navigation task (t2), writing task (t2), and prior beliefs posttest.

2.5 Analysis plan

Data analysis procedures for the prior beliefs questionnaire are first a general inspection of agreement with the statements: agreement was coded as -1 and disagreement as +1. Second, these values are multiplied by the degree of certainty (coded from 0 = very uncertain to 4 = very certain) for each item. Disagreement with the misconception or inaccurate information accompanied by a high degree of certainty is coded with a high positive

score, while agreement with a misconception or inaccurate information multiplied by a high degree of certainty is coded with a negative score, resulting in values ranging from -4 to +4. Responses followed by a degree of certainty of “very uncertain” receive a score of 0, even if correct, as they could be the result of guesswork.

For the analysis of eye movements collected during the navigation task at t1 and t2, areas of Interest will be defined in the Mangold software analyser corresponding to navigation (search engine features) and evaluation (website banner, author information, and reliable/non reliable texts). Analysis will be based on a comparison between fixation in equivalent Areas of Interest (AOIs) at t1 and t2. The measure extracted from the output is total fixation time, which is the sum of the fixation durations (ms) inside an AOI. Fixation times will be divided by the number of words per AOI to enable comparison across AOIs. Answers to the annotation sheet will be inspected as a manipulation checks, following the same procedures as previous eye tracking studies (Mason et al., 2015, Do Amaral et al., 2025).

The writing task will be analysed by identifying a) the position endorsed and b) the number of citations to reliable sources, following the same procedures as Salmerón et al. (2020). Two independent raters will analyse the sample. Disagreements are going to be solved through discussion.

Statistical analysis will be guided by the principle of null hypothesis testing applied to confirmatory factor analysis. No exploratory analyses will be undertaken. First, eye tracking data and scores in the writing task will be inspected for outliers (both at pre- and posttest). Linear regression models are going to be used for data analysis with the alpha threshold for hypothesis testing set to 0.05. In RQ1, the independent (predictor) variable is group (EMMEs/control) and the dependent (response) variables are fixation duration on a) the search engine results page and its embedded features, b) the source features within each webpage (banner and author’s photo, name, and occupation), and c) the reliable webpages (as opposed to non-reliable webpages). In RQ2, the independent variable is group (EMMEs/control) and the

dependent variable is a composite between position and citations in the writing task. Finally, for RQ3, pre/posttest differences will be fit in the model as response variables, with group as predictor. Bonferroni correction will be applied to correct for multiple comparisons across the three research questions.

In relation to the outlier identification in the eye fixation data, studies in eye tracking identify as outliers fixations departing more than 2-3 SD from individual means. Our threshold will be fixations that last two standard deviations above or below each participant fixation duration mean. These fixations will be replaced by the respective median. In relation to data distribution, time variables are commonly right-skewed, with skewness values higher than 0.5. If this is the case, the variables will be log-transformed to better approximate to a normal distribution.

2.6 Timeline

Table 5

Timeline for study completion and resubmission

	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sept	Oct
Eye tracking data treatment	X	X				
Coding – writing task			X	X		
Data cleaning – pre/posttests			X			
Statistical analysis			X	X	X	X
Manuscript writing	X	X	X	X	X	X
Manuscript resubmission						X

Source: authors

Authors contributions

Juliana do Amaral: funding acquisition, conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing. **Mailce Borges Mota:** funding acquisition, conceptualization, methodology, supervision, resources, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing.

Conflicts of interest

We have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Ethics committee approval

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the university (protocol number 7.469.720). The research questions and hypotheses were preregistered at the Open Science Framework platform (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TYCXK>).

Data availability statement

Data from the pilot study and instruments (questionnaire and essay tasks) to be used in data collection are openly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20215751>. Raw data, analysis scripts, and the code to be used for analysis will be deposited after data collection.

Preprint link

The protocol is available at [10.5281/zenodo.20208485](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20208485).

AI Use Statement

The authors declare that no AI tools were used in the creation of this manuscript or in any part of the work reported.

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